

Contrastive Learning for Whole Slide Image Representation: A Self-Supervised Approach in Digital Pathology

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ABSTRACT:

Image analysis in digital pathology is identified as a challenging field, particularly for AI-driven classification and search tasks. The high-resolution and large-scale nature of whole slide images (WSIs) present significant computational challenges in representing and analyzing these images effectively. The research endeavors to tackle these hurdles by presenting an innovative methodology grounded in self-supervised learning (SSL). Unlike prior SSL approaches that depend on augmenting at the patch level, the novel framework capitalizes on existing primary site information to directly glean effective representations from Whole Slide Images (WSIs). Moreover, the investigation integrates fully supervised contrastive learning to bolster the resilience of these representations for both classification and search endeavors. For experimentation, the study drew upon a dataset encompassing over 6,000 WSIs sourced from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) repository facilitated by the National Cancer Institute. The proposed architecture underwent training and assessment using this dataset. Evaluation primarily focused on scrutinizing performance across diverse primary sites and cancer subtypes, with particular attention dedicated to lung cancer classification. Impressively, the proposed architecture yielded outstanding outcomes, showcasing robust performance across the majority of primary sites and cancer subtypes. Furthermore, the study garnered the top position in validation for a lung cancer classification task.

Keywords: Digital Pathology, Whole Slide Image, Representation Learning, Self-Supervised Learning, Image Search.

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INTRODUCTION

The advent of digital pathology has heralded a new era in medical image analysis, particularly for diagnostic purposes [1]. Histopathology images, commonly referred to as whole slide images (WSIs), typically come with accompanying information detailing the site and type of diseases and malignancies. Recent advancements in digital technology have facilitated the rapid digital scanning of tissue slides, leading to the generation of high-quality WSIs. This technological progress has resulted in a significant increase in the volume of WSI archives stored in hospitals and clinics. Consequently, there has been a growing need for timely analysis of WSIs to meet the demands of

modern pathology workflows [2]. Therefore, digital slide scanning, in addition to other benefits offered by pathology digitization, has become essential in addressing these pressing needs. The rise of computerized techniques has made them a preferred approach for image analysis and diagnosis. Particularly, the field of digital pathology has undergone significant transformation, largely due to the recent advancements in artificial neural networks within the realm of AI as well as digital technology [3, 4]. Deep learning has emerged as a promising tool for various pathology tasks, including segmentation, classification of regions and nuclei, and searching among WSIs to identify similar morphology patterns. However, representing digitized pathology slides poses several challenges.

WSIs typically contain vast amounts of data, often with dimensions exceeding 50,000×50,000 pixels. Moreover, the morphological characteristics that distinguish different diagnoses can be microscopic, making it challenging to effectively represent WSIs. Traditionally, creating a single vector representation directly from a WSI has been explored using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). A common approach involves dividing the WSI into numerous small patches, processing each patch through a CNN, and then aggregating the output features to develop a single WSI representation for tasks such as search and classification. However, this patch-based feature extraction method may not be efficient due to its multi-stage architecture, and it often fails to capture important information about patch importance and spatial patch knowledge during the aggregation stage.

In this paper, the authors propose an end-to-end architecture with two main contributions. Firstly, they introduce an end-to-end self-supervised, attention-based multiple instance learning (SS-CAMIL) method. This approach leverages the primary site information of each WSI, which is typically available during tissue preparation and digitization. The SS-CAMIL method aims to learn representations directly from the WSIs while considering the importance of individual patches. Furthermore, the authors demonstrate the efficacy of employing a supervised contrastive learning approach to enhance the quality of model embeddings for both WSI classification and search tasks. This approach helps in learning semantically meaningful representations by pulling together instances of the same class while pushing apart instances of different classes in the embedding space. The proposed approach addresses some of the challenges associated with representing digitized pathology slides by introducing an end-to-end architecture that leverages self-supervised and supervised contrastive learning techniques to learn informative representations directly from WSIs.

RELATED WORK

Patch-Level WSI Representation

Patch-Level Whole Slide Image (WSI) Representation refers to methods aimed at characterizing WSIs by focusing on individual patches within them. Rather than analyzing the entire slide at once, these approaches break down the image into smaller patches and extract features from each patch to represent the overall slide. This technique allows for finer-grained analysis and enables the detection of subtle patterns and abnormalities within the slide. One early approach, as demonstrated by [5], involved iteratively extracting and classifying features from individual patches using CNNs. Subsequently, they employed a multi-label Support Vector Machine (SVM) to generate a single vector representation for the entire WSI, synthesizing information from the classified patches. Similarly, [6] conducted research where they extracted features from different magnification levels (20x and 5x) and aggregated these features by averaging the probabilities associated with corresponding patches. This multi-magnification approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the slide at different resolutions. Another technique, introduced by [7], involved clustering the entire tissue based on color clustering techniques. Patches were then selected based on the identified clusters, and patch-level embeddings were utilized for conducting WSI searches. This method leverages color information to group similar regions together, enabling efficient patch selection and subsequent analysis. These early representation approaches primarily focused on extracting features at the patch level within WSIs. They utilized various techniques such as iterative classification, multi-magnification feature extraction, and color clustering for patch selection. These methods aimed to create informative representations of WSIs suitable for tasks such as classification and search, enabling more effective analysis and interpretation of digital pathology images.

Multiple Instance Learning

Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) is a specialized learning framework where a label is assigned to a "bag" of instances rather than to individual instances, as first proposed by Dietterich et al. in 1997. In the context of digital pathology, MIL considers the representation of WSIs by treating each WSI as a bag containing multiple patches or instances. This enables the model to take into account the collective information from all patches within a slide when making predictions. A significant advancement in MIL is the introduction of deep MIL by [8], where various pooling layers following a specific form were demonstrated to produce permutation invariant representations. Since then, several MIL-based methods for WSI representation have been developed. For example, [9] proposed attention-based multiple instance learning, which involves performing weighted pooling over each instance feature to capture the most informative patches within a WSI. [10] achieved attention-based pooling in MIL using memory networks (MEM) to learn permutation invariant representations. In a different approach, [11] utilized graph Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to treat each patch as a node in a graph, learning an adjacency matrix to construct a graph representation of WSIs. More recently, [12] employed deep sets for MIL training in histopathology. They introduced a conditional prediction layer where predictions of primary site labels guide the primary diagnosis predictions. These approaches illustrate the versatility and effectiveness of MIL in handling WSIs. They leverage techniques such as attention-based pooling, graph representations, and deep learning architectures to enhance WSI representation and improve classification accuracy. MIL provides a powerful framework for learning from WSIs, enabling the development of models that can effectively analyze and interpret pathology images for various diagnostic tasks.

Self-Supervised Learning

Self-Supervised Learning (SSL) is a subset of deep learning techniques where a model is trained on pretext tasks derived directly from the data itself, without requiring human annotations. The primary objective of SSL is to learn representations or features from the data that can subsequently be applied to downstream tasks. In SSL, pretext tasks are carefully designed to encourage the model to learn meaningful representations of the input data. A pivotal work in vision-based SSL is by [13], where the authors introduce rotation classification as a pretext task. They demonstrate that training on this pretext task leads to improved performance on various computer vision tasks, including classification, object detection, and segmentation. SSL allows models to autonomously extract useful features from unlabeled data, which can then be fine-tuned for specific tasks. In the realm of histopathology, there has been increasing interest in patch-level self-supervision techniques. For example, [14] proposed pathology-specific pretext tasks such as magnification classification and JigMag, which involves predicting the order of magnification in a shuffled vector of different magnifications. Additionally, they introduced a task for predicting the hematoxylin channel, a crucial component in histopathology image analysis. Overall, SSL presents a promising approach for learning representations from unlabeled data, which can subsequently be applied to various downstream tasks in both general computer vision and domain-specific applications like histopathology. This technique holds significant potential for advancing automated analysis and understanding of complex datasets in diverse domains.

Contrastive Learning

Contrastive learning is a burgeoning field in machine learning research aimed at training models to discern similarities and differences between instances by pulling similar instances closer together and pushing dissimilar ones further apart. This is accomplished by optimizing a model using a contrastive loss function, which encourages the model to generate distinct feature representations for different inputs.

The concept of contrastive loss was initially introduced in a seminal work by [15]. They proposed a similarity loss function to map training data into a target space, such that the L1 norm of the target space reflects the semantic distance of the input space. This method involves pairwise comparison of inputs to determine whether to attract or repel samples based on their similarity.

[16] extended this idea by employing one instance as an anchor, along with one negative and one positive sample, for metric learning, rather than pairwise comparisons. [17] further developed the concept by suggesting a fully supervised contrastive loss, which aims to bring clusters of points

belonging to the same class closer together while pushing clusters of samples from other classes apart.

Recent advancements have seen contrastive learning predominantly implemented in a self-supervised manner. For example, [18] introduced SimCLR, a framework for contrastive learning of visual representations, which utilizes different augmentations as positive samples. In the context of pathology, [19] employed SimCLR and achieved notable results across various histopathology downstream tasks, such as classification, regression, and segmentation, compared to baseline training methods.

Overall, contrastive learning presents a robust approach for learning informative representations from data, with applications spanning diverse domains, including pathology. It has demonstrated promising results in improving model performance across a range of tasks by facilitating the learning of meaningful and discriminative features from the data.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper, we introduce a novel end-to-end self-supervised learning approach at the WSI level, using primary site information as the pretext task. The primary site information represents the organ type of each digital slide and is readily available for every WSI. Previous studies have treated primary site information as a "soft label." We demonstrate that leveraging primary site information for the pretext task enhances the model's ability to generalize in diagnosis classification tasks.

It can be seen from Figure 1 that the transferred knowledge of pretext task (e.g., for label "kidney" as the primary site) is used for the downstream task (e.g., for label "KIRP", kidney renal papillary cell carcinoma, as the primary diagnosis) are outlined with a grey line. For the LUAD/LUSC classification task, only the blocks on the right side the dashed red line is used for we will be using pre-trained features.

Figure 1. SS-CAMIL Concept

We also incorporate supervised contrastive learning to generate more robust representations at the WSI level. The methodology is presented step by step, with the complete process depicted in Figure 1. This figure illustrates the SS-CAMIL concept, where the knowledge transferred from the pretext task (e.g., using "kidney" as the primary site label) is utilized for downstream tasks (e.g., classifying "KIRP," kidney renal papillary cell carcinoma, as the primary diagnosis). The blocks outlined with a grey line indicate this transfer of knowledge. For tasks like LUAD/LUSC classification, only the blocks on the right side of the dashed red line in Figure 1 are employed, as pre-trained features are utilized. This ensures that the model leverages the learned representations effectively for specific diagnostic tasks. Our proposed method utilizes primary site information as a pretext task and incorporates supervised contrastive learning to improve WSI-level representations, ultimately enhancing the model's performance in diagnosis classification tasks.

Patch Selection

Patch selection in histopathology involves choosing relevant patches from WSIs to be used for training or analysis. In the method described by [20], a two-step k-means clustering approach is employed. In the first step, the tissue is grouped based on color histogram analysis. This initial clustering helps segment the tissue into distinct color regions. In the second step, a second k-means clustering is applied to the patch locations within each color segment identified in the first step. This step ensures the selection of spatially varied patches from each color segment. By considering both color and spatial distribution, this approach ensures that the selected patches represent diverse regions of the WSI. Each selected patch corresponds to a different location and color within the WSI, thereby ensuring that a wide range of regions from the WSI are included during training or analysis. This comprehensive coverage of the WSI

Feature Extraction

In the feature extraction phase, the order of patches is adjusted before being inputted into the feature extractor block. Let's break down the process: Reshape Layer: Each input undergoes a reshape operation, transforming its shape from (b, n, w, h) to $(b \times n, w, h)$. This reshaping effectively flattens the batch and patch dimensions while preserving the spatial dimensions of each patch. The reshaped patches are then fed into an EfficientNet B0 model, which is a convolutional neural network architecture optimized for both accuracy and efficiency in various image recognition tasks. The EfficientNet B0 model extracts features from the patches. The features obtained from the final convolutional block of the EfficientNet B0 model are processed through a global max-pooling layer and a fully connected layer. This process compresses the spatial information into high-dimensional feature vectors of size 1024 for each patch. Another reshape operation is applied to convert the output shape from $(b \times n, 1024)$ back to $(b, n, 1024)$. This step restores the original batch and patch dimensions while retaining the extracted feature vectors for further processing or analysis. This process involves reshaping the input patches, passing them through an EfficientNet B0 model for feature extraction, and reshaping the output to retain the original batch and patch dimensions while preserving the extracted feature vectors. This allows for efficient extraction and utilization of high-dimensional feature representations from the input patches.

Attention-Based Pooling

In the attention-based pooling process, the feature vectors obtained from the preceding stage are fed into an attention block. This attention block comprises two fully connected layers followed by an extension layer. These dense layers produce a mask of size (b, n) , where 'b' represents the number of batches and 'n' represents the number of patches. This mask is then duplicated to match the dimensionality of the feature vectors, resulting in a mask of size $(b, n, 1024)$, where 1024 corresponds to the dimensionality of the feature vectors. Subsequently, the mask is element-wise multiplied with the feature vectors, and the resulting values are averaged across the patch dimension (n). This averaging generates a single 1024-dimensional vector representation for each Whole Slide Image (WSI). This attention-based pooling mechanism dynamically weighs the importance of each patch in contributing to the WSI's representation. Unlike a simple average pooling layer where each patch contributes equally, the attention mechanism enables the model to learn the importance (weight) of each patch. This allows the model to focus more on patches that are considered more representative of the WSI. This means that the output representation remains the same regardless of the order in which the input patches are presented. This property offers flexibility in patch selection, as the model can effectively utilize different patch orders without affecting the final representation. This enhances the robustness and adaptability of the model, making it more resilient to variations in input data.

This paper makes two key contributions: Integration of Primary Site Information in Self-Supervised Learning (SSL): The main contribution of this approach lies in integrating primary site information as pseudo-labels within a self-supervised learning (SSL) framework during the initial training phase. Unlike previous SSL methods in pathology that relied on data augmentation-based self-supervision, this method utilizes existing primary site information from Whole Slide Images (WSIs) as pseudo-labels. Experimental findings indicate that incorporating this primary site information leads to performance improvements in the model. The impact of self-supervision is evaluated through two sets of experiments: firstly, by presenting results of basic attention-based Multiple Instance Learning

(MIL) without self-supervision (referred to as CAMIL), and secondly, by comparing these results with the performance achieved after incorporating primary site self-supervision into CAMIL (referred to as SS-CAMIL). Importantly, this self-supervision method operates in an end-to-end manner at the WSI level, distinguishing it from previous SSL methods that operated at the patch level. In summary, this approach enhances model performance by leveraging primary site information as pseudo-labels within a self-supervised learning framework, providing a novel way to improve the accuracy of histopathological image analysis. Feature Extraction for WSI Search and Classification: Finally, features extracted from the last fully connected layer before the projection head are used for WSI search and classification. This process improves the accuracy and efficiency of histopathological image analysis, as the model has been trained to extract relevant features for these tasks.

Utilization of Supervised Contrastive Learning (CL): The method involves using contrastive learning, where feature vectors extracted from WSIs are processed through a projection head. A contrastive loss function is applied, which compares feature vectors based on primary site labels. This approach helps the model learn to distinguish between different primary sites in the data. Utilizing contrastive learning in a Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) setup poses a challenge due to the need for large batch sizes. However, because WSIs are typically large, achieving large batch sizes can be impractical. To overcome this challenge, a cross-entropy loss is incorporated into the contrastive loss function. This additional loss function helps ensure that positive instances (WSIs with the same primary site) are positioned close to specific points in the embedding space, compensating for the limited number of positive samples within small batch sizes. Training on Downstream Tasks: After this initial training session, the model undergoes further training on downstream tasks using diagnostic labels (i.e., primary diagnosis). This step allows the model to learn additional features relevant to specific diagnostic tasks, enhancing its ability to perform classification and other analyses.

EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Dataset and Setup

The study utilized a dataset consisting of 6,746 WSIs obtained from TCGA (The Cancer Genome Atlas Program). The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets with proportions of 85%, 5%, and 10%, respectively, in accordance with ratios commonly used in benchmarking literature. During training, a batch size of 16 and a set size of 40 WSIs were employed. These WSIs covered 24 primary sites and included 30 different primary diagnoses. Patches were extracted from the WSIs at a size of 1000×1000 and then resized to 224×224 primarily due to memory constraints, a practice commonly observed in literature. Augmentation methods like horizontal and vertical flips, 90-degree rotations, shifting, and scaling were implemented through the Albumentations library. Training employed an exponential decay learning rate scheduler with a base of 0.96 and a coefficient of 0.0001, reducing the learning rate over epochs (0.0001×0.96 per epoch). Models underwent 150 epochs of training, utilizing three Tesla V100 GPUs in parallel. In contrastive learning tasks, a temperature of 0.1 was applied in both pretext and downstream tasks. During testing, horizontal and vertical WSI search tasks were conducted. The horizontal search aimed to classify tumor types across the entire test database, whereas the vertical search targeted the identification of specific cancer subtypes within slides from a single primary site. Both search tasks employed the k-NN algorithm with $k = 3$, utilizing the leave-one-out technique and presenting average scores due to the limited size of the test set. In addition, a classification task distinguishing between Lung Adenocarcinoma (LUAD) and Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma (LUSC) was performed on a distinct dataset consisting of 2,574 lung tissues. For this task, 1,800 slides were allocated for training, while 774 slides were reserved for testing. The convolutional feature extraction block was kept unchanged to showcase the previously learned features, with the batch size and set size maintaining consistency with the earlier setup.

WSI Search Results

The excerpt describes a comparison of search results for Whole Slide Images (WSI) across different models. It specifically focuses on comparing the performance of the model introduced in the paper

with two previous studies conducted by [20] and [21]. This comparison is detailed in two tables: Table 1 for horizontal search results and Table 2 for vertical search results.

In both tables, the performance of the model presented in the paper is contrasted with that of the models proposed by Kalra et al. and Hemati et al. This comparison provides insights into how the model introduced in the paper stacks up against previous approaches in terms of WSI search performance, offering valuable information for assessing advancements in the field.

CAMIL: This denotes the baseline model, an attention-based Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) framework integrating Contrastive Learning (CL) but excluding self-supervision. It acts as the benchmark for assessing the performance enhancement attained through the integration of self-supervision.

SS-CAMIL shares similarities with the CAMIL model in terms of its architectural design and utilization of contrastive learning (CL). However, what sets SS-CAMIL apart is its integration of self-supervision using primary site information. This means that in addition to the contrastive learning mechanism, SS-CAMIL also incorporates supervision signals derived from the primary site labels. During training, SS-CAMIL leverages the weights obtained from the self-supervision process. These weights are derived from the additional information provided by primary site labels and are utilized to enhance the model's learning process.

The provided explanation outlines the distinction between horizontal and vertical search tasks in the context of tumor type and subtype identification. Horizontal search involves identifying tumor types across the entire test database. In contrast, vertical search entails identifying the specific subtype of a cancer within slides from a single primary site. The comparison between CAMIL and SS-CAMIL in both horizontal and vertical search tasks serves the purpose of assessing the impact of incorporating self-supervision using primary site information. This comparison allows researchers to evaluate how the inclusion of self-supervision influences the model's performance in identifying tumor types and subtypes. By comparing the performance of SS-CAMIL with CAMIL, as well as with models proposed by [20] and [21], researchers can effectively evaluate and validate the effectiveness of the proposed approach. This comparative analysis helps in understanding the relative strengths and weaknesses of different models and methodologies in tumor type and subtype identification tasks, ultimately contributing to advancements in the field of pathology image analysis.

Table 1. Horizontal Search Results. F1-scores of Majority-3 (in %) are Reported

Tumor Type	nslides	Yottixel	CNN-DS	CAMIL	SS-CAMIL
Brain	46	73	91	100	100
Breast	77	45	77	91	91
Endocrine	71	61	66	86	89
Gastro.	69	50	75	84	86
Gynaec.	18	16	33	56	62
Head/neck	23	17	69	74	92
Liver	44	43	56	77	84
Melanocytic	18	16	50	61	78
Mesenchymal	12	8	100	92	92
Prostate/testis	44	47	81	91	89
Pulmonary	68	58	91	81	87
Urinary tract	112	67	76	92	95
Haematopoietic	42	0	24	50	50

We observe the performance of the SS-CAMIL model in horizontal search across different tumor types. Out of the four setups considered, SS-CAMIL achieves the best results in 10 out of 13 cases. In one of the remaining three cases (Prostate/Testis), the CAMIL model outperforms SS-CAMIL. However, SS-CAMIL still demonstrates competitive results across the rest of the tumor types. One notable observation is that, despite CNN-DS utilizing primary site information for tumor subtype classification, CAMIL performs better in most cases. This highlights the impact of attention-based pooling, which SS-CAMIL incorporates, as opposed to simple average pooling. Another significant observation is the performance improvement achieved with self-supervision on primary sites. In most

tumor types, SS-CAMIL outperforms CAMIL, suggesting that integrating primary site information within the self-supervision framework aids in better generalization when classifying subtypes.

Overall, the results indicate that SS-CAMIL exhibits superior performance in horizontal search tasks across various tumor types, emphasizing the effectiveness of attention-based pooling and self-supervision mechanisms.

Table 2. Vertical Search Results. F1-scores of Majority-3 (in %) are Reported

Tumor Type	Subtype	nslide's	Yottixel	CNN-DS	CAMIL	SS-CAMIL
Gastrointestinal tract	COAD STAD ESCA READ	22	62	69	72	73
		27	61	64	79	92
		10	12	44	55	89
		10	30	45	26	0
Pulmonary	LUAD LUSC MESO	30	62	6	71	76
		35	69	60	76	75
		3	0	50	50	33
Liver, pancreaticobiliary	LIHC PAAD CHOL	32	82	95	95	95
		8	94	94	94	94
		4	26	0	0	0
Endocrine	THCA PCPG ACC	50	92	98	99	100
		15	61	81	86	90
		6	25	28	50	77
Urinary tract	KIRP KIRC BLCA KICH	25	75	84	84	88
		47	91	87	92	92
		31	89	95	94	98
		9	70	53	88	80
Brain	LGG GBM	23	78	89	91	89
		23	82	89	91	90
Prostate/testis	PRAD TGCT	31	98	97	94	100
		13	96	93	96	100
Gynaecological	OV CESC UCS	9	80	82	76	80
		6	92	66	44	44
		3	75	88	100	50

It shows the performance of the SS-CAMIL model in vertical search, particularly across different subtypes of tumors. Out of a total of 24 distinct subtypes, SS-CAMIL achieved the best F1-score in 16 subtypes. The subtypes BLCA, THYM, HNSC, SARC, SKCM, and UVM are not included in the table because they represent the only subtype in their respective tumor types. However, in five subtypes, the CAMIL model performed better. The text notes that a common trend emerges when the model doesn't perform well, which is the presence of small sample sizes. This suggests that when dealing with subtypes with limited data, the model may struggle to learn distinctive features. Furthermore, it highlights the impact of self-supervision (SS) on model performance, indicating that in 15 subtypes, SS has helped the model perform better than CAMIL. This implies that the self-supervision mechanism aids in improving the model's performance across various subtypes. To illustrate the effect of contrastive learning (CL), the authors provide a visual representation in the form of a 2D t-SNE plot comparing SS-CAMIL with the approach proposed by Hemati et al. from 2021 (referred to as CNN-DS) in Figure 2. The plot demonstrates that the clusters formed by SS-CAMIL are tighter and more separable compared to those formed by CNN-DS, indicating that the contrastive learning component contributes to better feature representation and clustering in SS-CAMIL.

LUAD/LUSC Classification

We discuss the results of a classification task focusing on distinguishing between two types of lung cancer, LUAD (Lung Adenocarcinoma) and LUSC (Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma). The features utilized for this classification are extracted from a DenseNet model, as referenced in a previous study by 'Hemati' et al. from 2021. The authors demonstrate that their proposed strategy for classification outperforms previous approaches by achieving an accuracy of 88%, which is 2% higher than the earlier methods. This improvement highlights the efficacy of employing attention-pooling and contrastive learning techniques in the classification task. The attention-pooling mechanism allows

the model to focus on relevant features, while contrastive learning helps in learning more discriminative representations, ultimately contributing to the enhanced performance in distinguishing between LUAD and LUSC.

Figure 2. t-SNE of CNN-DS [21] (left) and SS-CAMIL (right)

Table 3. Attention Pooling Scores of 9 different WSIs.

Weighting	Lung	Kidney	Brain
	1 :2: 3	1:2:3	1:2:3
Uniform	0.97	0.89	0.94
	0.89	0.70	0.87
	0.80	0.89	0.88
SS-CAMIL	0.98	0.91	0.96
	0.90	0.79	0.86
	0.83	0.91	0.90

We mention the utilization of SS-CAMIL blocks in the task, which resulted in an improvement in performance to 89%. However, the authors express uncertainty regarding whether the SS-CAMIL blocks have been exposed to the data in the search task. Both datasets used in the study are sourced from the TCGA repository. Due to this uncertainty, the authors chose not to include the performance numbers associated with the SS-CAMIL blocks in the table. This decision likely stems from the desire to maintain transparency and accuracy in reporting results, acknowledging the potential influence of data exposure on the performance improvement observed with the SS-CAMIL blocks.

Attention Pooling Effectiveness

We have an investigation about the effectiveness of the attention-pooling layer within the model. We selected nine random WSIs from organs like the Lung, Kidney, and Brain. They enlisted the expertise of a pathology specialist to evaluate the usefulness of patches within each WSI, rating them on a scale of 1 to 3, where 1 indicates "not useful," 2 denotes "somewhat useful," and 3 signifies "very useful." To assess the effectiveness of the attention-pooling layer, we multiplied the normalized scores (reflecting the usefulness of each patch) by the output of the attention block for each WSI. They then compared these results with a scenario where all patches were assigned uniform importance (i.e., all patches having the same weight). Next, they divided the obtained scores by the optimal importance scores (where the weights of patches are proportional to their effectiveness label). This process yielded normalized numbers, which were then analyzed and presented in Table 3. The findings suggest that the model has effectively learned the relative importance of patches within the attention block, demonstrating its ability to discern and prioritize patches based on their significance in the WSI analysis task.

CONCLUSION

The paper introduces a groundbreaking self-supervised multiple instance learning model that makes use of primary site information. This model is designed to generate representations at the level of WSIs. The study demonstrates that the proposed WSI-level representation model exhibits superior generalization capabilities when compared to two existing approaches. It suggests that the model is effective at capturing essential features and patterns within WSIs, enabling better performance in distinguishing between different tumor subtypes. The proposed model's performance is assessed through two primary tasks: WSI search and classification. The findings demonstrate that the model excels in both tasks, showcasing dominant performance. This implies that the model is highly effective at accurately identifying tumor types across entire datasets and accurately classifying different tumor subtypes within individual slides. In summary, the paper demonstrates how the proposed self-supervised multiple instance learning model enhances the generalization and performance of WSI analysis tasks, thereby making significant contributions to the field of pathology image analysis.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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